

RETHINKING TRANSPORTATION MOBILITY AND SOCIAL EQUITY POLICY IN LAGOS METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the Study: The study attempt to examine transportation mobility and social equity policies in metropolitan Lagos.

Design/Methodology: The study employed the interpretivist philosophy also known as qualitative or phenomenological research approach in data collection. Primary data were generated mainly through key informant interviews, while secondary data were gathered from the internet, journals, newspaper editorials, transportation policy documents, and other government publications. Key informant interviews were conducted with officers from the Lagos State Ministry of Transportation. The acquired data was analysed using a content analytic approach.

Findings: Findings of the study revealed that population growth in the state's sub-urban and rural areas has put pressure on the city's infrastructure, especially its transportation system, necessitating a rethinking of transportation mobility.

Practical Implications: Government must invest heavily in public transport services in suburban and rural areas through public-private partnerships (PPPs) in order to improve the quality and expand the state's public transport network. The study further asserted that the state government's must invest in transportation infrastructure, public transportation subsidies, and the city's light rail system be expanded in sub-urban and rural areas so as to achieve improved transportation mobility and social equity in the state.

Originality/value: The current study makes a substantial contribution as well filled the gap to the extant literature in public transport services in suburban and rural areas through public-private partnerships in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Metropolitan; Rethinking Transportation; Service Delivery; Social Equity Policy; Transportation Infrastructure.

Paper type: Research paper

1. INTRODUCTION

Transportation infrastructure that is well-planned is critical to economic activities in both developed and developing nations all over the world. It determines urban growth patterns that

allow the movement of products and services, as well as guaranteeing fair access to opportunities for people (Adagunodo&Filani, 2023). A better transport network in Lagos will boost connections between firms, workers, and markets, promoting economic growth and productivity. Folorunso and Oyesiku (2023) opine that efficient transit decreases travel time and expenses, allowing firms to function more efficiently and workers to more quickly access job opportunities. Furthermore, a dependable and economical public transportation system may connect underprivileged neighbourhoods to vital services, education, and job hubs, fostering social inclusion. Scholars like Akinseye (2020) argues that the transport mobility and social equity policy in Lagos are complicated, complex, and challenging. It is instructive to note that the city has a rapidly growing population, and its transportation infrastructure is struggling to keep up. As a result, traffic congestion, pollution, and safety problems have arisen (Owoeye & Ogunsanwo, 2022). The state has a population of over 23 million people, and its transportation infrastructure is severely underutilized (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022).

The transportation challenges in Lagos are also exacerbated by the city's social inequality. People living in low-income areas are more likely to rely on public transportation, which is frequently unreliable and congested. Besides, the high cost of developing and maintaining transportation infrastructure is exigent (Folorunso&Oyesiku, 2023). Due to its low resources, Lagos has little money available for transit development. Investing in new infrastructure and transportation technologies, such as bike lanes and mass transit systems, becomes difficult as a result. Traffic congestion is also a major problem in the city, and many residents lack access to affordable and reliable transportation system (Akinola, 2019). There is no doubt that lack of transportation mobility also has a detrimental impact on social equity. People who live in low-income areas or on the outskirts of the city often have difficulty accessing jobs, schools, and other essential services. This has led to increase in the level of poverty, unemployment, and other social problems (NBS, 2022).

Lagos is a highly unequal city, with a large gap from the wealthy to the impoverished. This gap is reflected in the city's transportation system. The rich have access to private transportation, whereas the poor rely on fragmented and insufficient public transit infrastructure (NBS, 2022). However, the public transportation system has a variety of transportation modes, including buses, trains, ferries, and motorcycles, but these modes are not properly integrated (Oni & Odugbesan, 2020). This makes navigating the city difficult and time-consuming, particularly for those who rely on public transport. Another element contributing to Lagos' transportation challenges is the city's informal economy (Agbolade, 2020). The informal sector employs a considerable city's workforce, which means that they are not employed by the formal sector. This makes it difficult for them to access formal transportation services (Duru, 2022).

As a result, a high number of people live in informal settlements, making it difficult to adopt and enforce transit laws that meet the requirements of all inhabitants. Furthermore, people with disabilities also face significant challenges getting around the city. Also, because the state transportation policy is currently fragmented, with several government bodies accountable for different components of the system (Adagunodo&Filani, 2023), there is a lack of coordination between different levels of government. This makes comprehensive and integrated transportation solutions difficult to deploy. There is resistance to change from existing stakeholders (Akinola, 2019). Private operators dominate the transportation sector in Lagos, and they frequently have a strong interest in sustaining the status quo (Adeoye&Afolabi, 2021). This resistance can make it

difficult to implement new policies that would increase the effectiveness and equity of the system of transportation.

The state government has acknowledged the significance of transportation mobility and social equity. In 2021, the government released a new transportation policy tagged: Rethinking Transportation Mobility and Social Equity Policy in Metropolitan Lagos, which according to Duru (2022) can be regarded as a bold and ambitious policy (Duru, 2022). The policy has the potential to make a significant improvement in the transportation mobility of all residents of Lagos, regardless of their income level or where they live. It will also promote social equity by ensuring that all residents have access to affordable and reliable transportation, as well as reduce congestion and pollution, and improve road safety (Lagos Metropolitan Area Transport Authority, 2020).

Studies such as Adagunodo and Filani (2023), Adeoye and Afolabi (2021), Akinseye (2020), Akinola (2019), Agbolade (2020), Afolayan and Afolabi (2019) and other credible scholarship have attempted to come up with suggestions on how aforementioned challenges can be ameliorated, however, none of these studies has focused on the affordability impact of innovative financing mechanisms to fund transport projects in the state's sub-urban and rural areas. It is this identified gap in the extant literature that this study intend to fill. Based on this, the study examines rethinking transportation mobility and social equity policy in metropolitan Lagos.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In specific terms, the objectives are to:

1. Analysescreative financial techniques to finance rural and suburban transportation projects in the state.
2. Review the informal transportation sector of the city into state transportation policy.
3. Assess the integrated and multimodal transportation system throughout the state's suburban and rural areas.

3.LITERATURE REVIEW

Rethinking transportation mobility and social equity policy requires a thorough strategy that tackles the root reasons for transportation inequities and promotes inclusive and equitable transportation systems. Meanwhile, transportation mobility and social equity are two important aspects of urban planning and policy. Transportation mobility refers to the ability of people to move around a city or region, while social equity refers to the fair and just distribution of resources and opportunities.

3.1 Innovative Financial Strategies to Fund Transportation Projects in the State's Suburban and Rural Areas

Lagos State Government has explored more traditional funding sources, such as grants, loans, and taxes to fund transportation projects in the state (African Development Bank, 2021). However, traditional funding sources can be difficult to secure for transportation projects in suburban and ruraareas, as these areas are often seen as less profitable to investors (Arimah, 2021). Also, traditional funding sources may not be sufficient to meet the state's growing transportation needs. LAMATA (2020) asserted that with a combination of innovative and traditional funding strategies, the state government can secure the funding needed to improve transportation infrastructure and services in suburban and rural areas (Oni &Odugbesan, 2020).

This will help to establish a more just, accessible, and environmentally friendly transit system available to the citizens of Lagos State.

Duru (2022) identified some innovative financial strategies to fund transportation projects in Lagos State's suburban and rural areas:

3.2 Public-private partnerships (PPPs): PPPs are agreements in which the public and private sectors enter into contracts whereby the private sector offers financing, construction, and/or operation of public infrastructure (Owoeye & Ogunsanwo, 2022). PPPs have been used to finance a variety of transportation projects around the world, including the Lagos Mega City. The Lekki-Epe Motorway was funded through a PPP arrangement in between the Lagos state both a government and a consortium of private investors (Arimah, 2021). Also, the Lagos-Ibadan Motorway is being funded through another PPP arrangement between Nigeria's federal government and a consortium of private investors (Oni & Odugbesan, 2020). The expressway is being built and operated by the commercial sector, as well as the residents will pay a toll to the private industry to make use of the expressway once it is completed. Furthermore, the Eko Atlantic City development is being funded through a combination of private investment and value-capturing financing. The development is being built on reclaimed land, and the Lagos state government will capture a portion of the increase in property values that is generated by the development to help finance the project (World Bank, 2020).

3.3 Value Capture Financing (VCF): This is a way to finance public infrastructure and transportation projects by capturing the increase in property values that is generated by the project (Akinseye, 2020). VCF can be implemented through a variety of mechanisms, such as Special assessment districts, development impact fees, and tax increment financing (TIF) (SADs). The Lagos Metropolitan Area Transport Authority (LAMATA) is using VCF to finance the construction of the Lagos Light Rail project (LAMATA, 2022). VCF has been used to fund a number of transportation projects in Lagos State, including the Lekki-Epe Motorway and the Eko Atlantic City development.

3.4 Transportation Infrastructure Bonds: Transportation infrastructure bonds are a type of municipal bond that is used to finance transportation projects. These bonds can be classified into three types: impact bonds, diaspora bonds, and community bonds (Agbolade, 2020). Impact bonds are a type of pay-for-success financing in which Investors give money up front financing for societal programmes and are repaid depending on the accomplishment of specified goals. Impact bonds have been used to finance a variety of social programmes around the world, including transportation programmes (Akinseye, 2020). The Lagos state government is considering using impact bonds to finance the construction of new bus terminals in suburban and rural areas (LAMATA, 2022). The diaspora bonds are a type of bond that is sold to members of a diaspora community in order to raise money for development projects in their home country (Akinola, 2019). Diaspora bonds have been used to fund transportation projects in several African nations, Nigeria among others. Finally, the community bonds are a type of debt financing in which investors lend money to community-based organisations to finance local projects (CTAN, 2023). Community bonds have been employed to finance a variety of initiatives, such as transportation projects. The Community Transportation Association of Nigeria (CTAN) is using community bonds to finance the purchase of new buses for rural communities in Lagos State.

3.5.Crowd funding: This is a type of fundraising that uses the internet to raise money from a large number of people. Crowd funding can be used to fund a variety of transportation projects, such as bike lanes, pedestrian walkways, and public transit improvements.

3.6.Microfinance: This is a type of financial firm that gives low-income people small loans and businesses. Microfinance loans can be used to fund a variety of transportation needs, such as purchasing a vehicle or starting a transportation business.

In addition to these innovative financial strategies, the state can fund the transportation projects that are needed to improve mobility and economic opportunity in suburban and rural areas; likewise, the government could intensify efforts on traditional funding sources, such as government bonds and grants from international development organisations, for a more equitable, accessible, and sustainable transportation system for all residents of the state, irrespective of their social strata.

3.7 Informal transportation sector and the state transportation policy

The Lagos State Government has recognised the significance of the informal transportation sector in the city's transportation system and is working to incorporate it into its transportation policy. In 2018, the government launched the Lagos Urban Transport Reform Project (LUTRP), which aims to Boost the effectiveness and safety of the city's system of transportation (Afolayan&Idowu, 2022). According to a 2018 study by the World Bank, over 2 million people are directly employed in the informal transportation sector in Lagos (World Bank, 2022). Hence, it provides employment and income for a large number of people. This transportation sector has a crucial part in the transportation system of the state, as it is estimated that over 80% of all passenger trips on a daily basis in the state are made using informal modes of transportation, such as minibuses (Danfos), motorcycles (Okadas), tricycles (KekeMarwas), and boats (Oduola&Afolayan, 2023). However, the sector is largely unregulated and often operates in unsafe and inefficient conditions, as the sector is characterised by its flexibility, affordability, and accessibility (Akinola, 2019). It provides transportation to areas They are not serviced by official means of transportation, and it is often the only option for low-income residents (Alcorn, 2019).

Afolayan (2021) asserted that the informal sector is often seen as a threat to formal modes of transportation. Also, the sector is largely unregulated. This can lead to safety concerns as well as traffic congestion and pollution as shown in appendix I. Oduola and Afolayan (2023) identified a strategic mode the government can adopt to incorporate the informal transportation sector of the city into state transportation policy. These include:

3.8. Conducting a comprehensive assessment of the informal transportation sector. This assessment should include information on the size and scope of the sector, the types of vehicles used, the routes served, and the socioeconomic characteristics of the operators. This can be achieved by establishing a working group or task force to develop and implement a plan for incorporating the informal transportation sector into Lagos State transportation policy. The working group should include representatives from the Lagos State government, the informal transportation sector, and other stakeholders.

3.9. Drivers' training and certification programmes: The government should provide training and certification programmes for informal transportation drivers to improve their knowledge and skills. The training programme should cover topics such as road safety regulations, traffic laws,

and customer service. This would help to ensure that informal transportation operators are meeting minimum safety and service standards and that their vehicles are in good condition.

3.10. Provision of designated parking and loading areas: The government should provide designated routes, parking, and loading areas for informal transportation vehicles to improve traffic flow and safety, as it will reduce traffic congestion and improve efficiency. This can be achieved by developing dedicated infrastructure to support informal modes of transportation and by developing intermodal transfer facilities. This will integrate the informal transportation sector into the formal transportation system.

3.11. Subsidies for fuel and spare parts: Government can also provide subsidies to informal transportation operators to help them reduce their costs. Based on this, the subsidies will assist operators in purchasing fuel-efficient and environmentally friendly vehicles, as it will help reduce the reliance on private cars and improve the overall transportation system in the city.

Furthermore, the incorporation of the informal transportation sector into Lagos State transportation policy is essential to improving the overall transportation system in the city. It is essential to recognise that the informal sector meets a real need in the city, and any attempt to incorporate the informal sector into Lagos State transportation policy must be done in a way that is mutually beneficial to the informal sector and the formal sector. More so, the state must ensure that all residents of the city have access to safe, affordable, and efficient transportation.

3.12 Integrated and multimodal transportation system in the state's suburban and rural areas.

Building a better integrated and multimodal transportation system throughout the rural and suburban sections of the state requires good road infrastructure, which is essential for the efficient flow of commodities and people (Adeniran, 2023). Lagos State Government has been investing to improve the quality of roads and bridges, as well as building new roads to connect suburban and rural areas to urban centers. The state government has invested in expanding and improving public transportation services, such as buses and trains (LSG, 2021). This includes building new bus and train lines as well as improving the frequency and reliability of existing services. Yet, there is a need to invest more, as it is essential for the sustainable development of the state (Afolayan&Idowu, 2022).

Public transportation is the backbone of any integrated system of transportation, as it is pertinent to emphasise that the transport system should be integrated across different modes of transport, such as buses, trains, ferries, and para-transit services (Akinola, 2019). This will offer a multitude of distinct methods of transport to fulfill the requirements of different users, allow passengers to easily and efficiently switch between modes, and make it easier to plan and travel long distances (Oduola&Afolayan, 2023). Buses are a good option for short-distance travel, while trains are a good option for long-distance travel. Ferries can be useful for crossing bodies of water, and para-transit services can provide last-mile connectivity (Adeniran, 2023).

It is important to consider accessibility, affordability, and sustainability. The system should be accessible to all users, including people with disabilities and the elderly (World Bank, 2019). This means that vehicles and stations should be designed with universal accessibility in mind as well as affordability for all users. This means that fares should be set at a level that is affordable for the average person (Akinola, 2019). More so, the transportation system should be sustainable, both environmentally and economically. This means using low-emission vehicles and fuels and

designing the system to be efficient and cost-effective (Oduola&Afolayan, 2023). Meanwhile, a better integrated and multimodal transportation system can be incorporated into the Lagos state transportation plan In the rural and suburban sections of the state, as most residents are not aware of advantages of an integrated transportation system (Adeniran, 2023). The state government needs to keep the public informed about the benefits of using public transportation and other modes of non-motorised transportation. This can be achieved as long as the state government can Promote the usage of public transportation by offering subsidies to public transportation operators and by implementing policies that discourage the use of private vehicles, such as congestion pricing (World Bank, 2022).

Afolayan and Idowu (2022) highlight how integrated and multimodal transportation systems can be implemented in suburban and rural regions within the state. This according to them include:

3.13 Demand-responsive transit (DRT): This is a type of public transportation system that operates on a flexible schedule and route based on the needs of riders. This can be a particularly effective way to provide service in low-density areas, where traditional fixed-route bus service may not be feasible.

3.14 Micro-transit: It is a type of shared mobility service that uses small vehicles, such as vans or shuttles, to transport riders on demand. Micro-transit can be a good way to connect riders to public transportation or other destinations, such as jobs, schools, and markets.

3.15 Transit-oriented development (TOD): This is a type of development that is designed to be easily accessible by public transportation. Walking, biking, and cycling are healthy and sustainable ways of mobility. TOD can help reduce car dependence and create more vibrant and livable communities.

3.16 Complete streets: Complete roadways are made to accommodate all users, such as bikes, pedestrians, and motorists, and transit riders. This can involve adding features such as crosswalks, bike lanes, and bus shelters. The government is now promoting non-motorised transportation by building sidewalks and bike lanes, which is creating a safe and welcoming environment for pedestrians and cyclists as it is viewed as a healthy and sustainable way to get around.

4. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A variety of theories have been put forth to rethink transportation mobility and social equity policy. The study is anchored on efficiency-based theories and transportation justice theory.

4.1 Efficiency-based theories: One of the most prominent efficiency-based theories is intelligent transportation systems (ITS). Intelligence Transport Systems (ITS) are systems that use information technology to increase the effectiveness of the transportation networks. ITS proponents argue that ITS can aid in saving money, reducing transportation congestion, and improving air quality (Marcuse, 2009). Another efficiency-based theory is new urbanism. New urbanism is a movement that promotes the development of walkable, bikeable, and transit-oriented communities (Owens, 2013). New urbanism proponents argue that new urbanist communities are more sustainable and livable than traditional suburban communities.

4.2 Transportation Justice Theory: Transportation justice is a framework that advocates for equitable and sustainable transportation systems. This theory emphasises the need to address the historical and systemic injustices that have created unequal transportation access and outcomes for different groups of people (Dant, 2016). The theory focuses on the right to mobility for

everyone, irrespective of their income, race, ethnicity, gender, disability, or other factors (Akinola, 2019). It emphasises the need for transportation systems that are affordable, accessible, reliable, and safe for everyone. It calls for transportation policies that are fair, equitable, and sustainable and that empower marginalised communities to have a voice in transportation planning and decision-making (Blumenberg&Hasselbach, 2018), and this can be achieved by identifying and addressing transportation disparities, incorporating equity goals into planning processes, and observing and assessing outcomes to guarantee that they are equitable (Curtis, 2013). It is based on this that those who are mostly affected by transportation decisions should have a say in shaping those decisions. Transportation justice proponents argue that transportation systems should be designed to meet the needs of all people, regardless of their race, class, or income.

Meanwhile, each theory has its strengths and weaknesses, and There isn't a solution that works for everyone to the challenges of transportation mobility and social equity. It is also important to note that these theories are not mutually exclusive, and by considering the different theories that have been developed, we can begin to develop more equitable and sustainable transportation systems. Ultimately, the best approach to rethinking transportation mobility and social equity policy is to develop policies They are customized to meet the unique requirements of every community.

5.RESEARCH METHODS

The study examines rethinking transportation mobility and social equity policy in metropolitan Lagos, with specific reference to Lagos State, Nigeria. The interpretivism paradigm serves as the study's philosophical foundation. A qualitative method was used to gather data for the study. A design for exploratory research was considered appropriate for the research because of its flexibility to consider many different aspects of the phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Grey, 2017). This research design was used to discover the government's creative financial techniques to finance rural and suburban transportation projects in the state, especially in areas incorporating the informal transportation sector of the city into state transportation policy. Information was acquired from primary and secondary sources together. Primary information was produced using the key informant interviews method, as residents of the suburban and rural state officials in the Lagos State Ministry of Transportation were the subjects of the key informant interviews, which were purposefully selected based on their involvement in the transportation policy process in the state. We collected secondary data from journals, articles, newspapers, and other publications. Multiple secondary sources were used to reduce the risk of error and improve the study's reliability and validity. The collected data were content-analysed as the study adhered to the qualitative model of social research.

6.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The key informant interviews revealed that for the government to achieve creative financial techniques to finance transportation initiatives, Lagos State must adopt and embrace emerging financial techniques to finance rural and suburban transportation projects in the state. These strategies include impact investing aims to produce economic and/or social, and effect on the environment. Impact investors may be interested in investing in transportation projects that provide benefits to suburban and rural communities, whereas both the federal and state governments can make funds available in the form of grants to fund transportation projects in suburban and rural areas. These grants can be used to fund a variety of projects, such as road

construction, public transit improvements, and safety enhancements. Also, seek financial collaboration among private sector investors to invest as operators in public transportation investments. This can be done through a variety of methods, such as outsourcing funds from the capital market, which can have a long-term payment moratorium, and a public-private partnership mode of financing.

The findings of the study reflect the analytical data analyses based on the data gathered from the extant literature. Furthermore, the state government should incorporate sustainability-linked financing (SLF) methods on environmental, social, and governance (ESG) into the loan or bond issuance. This approach can encourage sustainable transportation practices while also attracting investors with ESG considerations. The above finding is in line with the views of Alcorn (2019), AfDB (2021), and CTAN (2023) on community bond programmes to finance transportation projects in rural Lagos State, which stated that emerging technologies can be monetized to support transportation projects. This approach can provide a revenue stream while also improving the efficiency and effectiveness of transportation systems in suburban and rural communities. This viewpoint is consistent with the research findings of Objective I.

Meanwhile, the findings uncovered the state's position in incorporating the informal transportation sector of the city into state transportation policy. The state needs to formalise the sector by developing regulations and standards for informal transportation providers, such as requiring them to obtain licences, undergo safety training, and maintain their vehicles in good condition. Furthermore, the study reveals the need for the government to provide support to informal transportation providers. This could include providing access to affordable financing, training, and other resources to help them improve their operations. The findings of the study also reflect the analytical data analyses based on the data gathered from the extant literature. The above finding is consistent with the views of Afolayan (2021) and Arimah (2021) on Mobility, transit, and social justice in Lagos, Nigeria: The Role of Informal Transportation Systems. They stated that integrating informal transportation into the formal transportation system would involve developing dedicated lanes or terminals for informal transportation providers and coordinating their schedules with formal transportation services. This would make it easier for passengers to transfer between different modes of transportation in terms of schedule coordination. This viewpoint is consistent with the research findings of Objective II.

In addition, a review of the integrated and multimodal transportation system throughout the rural and suburban sections of the state has not been the same in the urban area based on the social equity in the state. The government needs to invest massively in suburban and rural infrastructure that supports multimodal transportation systems, as it may involve partnerships with private companies. This includes building and maintaining high-quality roads, bike lanes, and sidewalks, as well as providing safe and convenient access to public transportation. This can be achieved by expanding public transportation services to suburban and rural areas by adding new routes and providing on-demand transportation options by increasing the frequency of service. The findings of the study reflect the analytical data analysis based on the data gathered from the existing literature. The above finding further confirmed the need for multimodal transportation, as the Lagos State government is currently developing and integrating the multimodal transportation system in the state. The results aligned with recent studies (such as Adeniran, 2023; and Duru, 2022), who noted that public-private partnerships (PPP) can become a pivot to shared mobility options as they will help to fill the gaps in public transportation

coverage in the state's rural and suburban communities. This viewpoint is consistent with the research findings of Objective III.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Findings from the study have obviously shown that population growth in the state's sub-urban as well as rural regions has put pressure on the city's infrastructure, especially its transportation system, necessitating a rethinking of transportation mobility. The study found that innovative and emerging financial strategies to finance initiatives related to transportation in the state must be fully embraced, especially in the rural and suburban parts of the state. The government must invest heavily in public transport services in suburban and rural areas through public-private partnerships (PPPs) in order to improve the quality and expand the state's public transport network. The study further asserted that the state government's system of discounted fares will make transportation more affordable and accessible to low-income residents. In conclusion, the study complements existing studies and spotlights new approaches to promoting sustainable transportation mobility in the state's rural and suburban areas. The study is an innovation for the government so as to attract foreign and domestic investors to invest in rural and suburban areas transportation systems inside the state. This can enhance the economic growth of the area.

The study recommended that a policy document be designed to capture transportation mobility and social equity policies in the state, especially in underprivileged economic areas. Also, the policy document should clearly state how the government will protect investors' interests in this area in terms of tax holidays, infrastructure provisions, etc. The document must be able to empower the Lagos State Driver Institute to develop regulations and standards for informal transportation providers, such as requiring them to obtain licences, undergo safety training, maintain their vehicles in good condition, and also to adopt emerging technologies in operational activities. This will help to create a more sustainable, accessible, and equitable transportation system for all residents of Lagos State. The study further suggests that investments in transportation infrastructure, public transportation subsidies, and the city's light rail system should be expanded in sub-urban and rural areas so as to achieve improved transportation mobility and social equity in the state.

8. CONTRIBUTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study definitely adds to the body of knowledge, as this aspect of transportation mobility and social equity policy has not been sufficiently researched in Nigeria. More so, the study created opportunities for investors who are willing to invest in this area in Nigeria. However, it was piloted in Lagos metropolis and may not represent the rest of the country's suburban and rural areas if such a study is carried out.

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